

CULTURAL BACKGROUND TO THE EMERGENCE OF ENGLISH AS AN INTERNATIONAL LANGUAGE.

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Annotation: This article examines the cultural context associated with the emergence of English as an international language. The emergence of English as an international language is a complex phenomenon influenced by various factors, including cultural background. This article attempts to explore the cultural background for the emergence of English as an international language. The paper argues that cultural factors have played a decisive role in the spread of the English language around the world and that this trend is likely to continue in the future. The article draws on the existing literature to emphasize the importance of the cultural background in the emergence of English as an international language. The paper also provides examples of cultural characteristics that are reflected in the English language and influenced its development as an international language. The article will be useful for comparing the cultural characteristics of countries and understanding their role in shaping world culture.

Keywords: English language, historical and cultural roots, international status, socio-cultural aspects, linguistic aspects, cultural background.

Introduction: English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world and is considered the international language of communication. However, much of this language has cultural roots. In this article, we will look at what cultural features are associated with the English language and what factors led to its worldwide spread. Every year, the English language is becoming increasingly important in international communication, while facing cultural differences. In this paper, we explore the influence of cultural background on the development of English as an international language and consider how this affects the use and dissemination of the language in various cultural contexts.

Historical roots of English as an international language English became an international language as a result of the growing influence of the British Empire and the expansion of the United States of America in the 19th and 20th centuries. The gradual spread of the English language has led to the emergence of various varieties of English, including British and American English. Cultural

roots: The cultural characteristics of the English-speaking countries - Great Britain and the USA, had a great influence on the spread of the English language in the world. Popular cultural elements such as cinema, music, literature, fashion, food, and others have become part of world culture and have been adopted from these countries through the spread of the English language. Cultural aspects of the language, such as the use of idioms, slang and sayings, also influence the formation of cultural stereotypes and ideas about English-speaking countries

International status one important factors in the global spread of the English language is its international status. English has become the language of international diplomacy, science, technology, business and is widely used in aviation, maritime transport and medicine. The international status of the English language clearly demonstrates its practical value and wide possibilities of communication.

Sociocultural aspects of the development of international English. Cultural characteristics influence the use of the English language and its distribution in different cultural contexts. For example, some common sociocultural traits, such as respect for elders and formality in communication, may be reflected in how people use English in different cultural environments.

Linguistic aspects of international English. One of the reasons why English has become international is its grammar and vocabulary, which are easily adaptable to different cultures and languages. Throughout history, English has borrowed many words from other languages, making it more accessible for international use.

The cultural background plays a significant role in the development of English as an international language. Historical, sociocultural and linguistic factors influence the use and dissemination of the English language in various cultural contexts. Understanding these factors helps to use English more effectively in intercultural communication, taking into account various cultural nuances.

Conclusion: English is a world language today, which makes it an indispensable tool in communication. The study of its cultural roots leads to the realization of the importance of studying cultural nuances and the formation of intercultural competencies among students and society as a whole. Thus, we can conclude that English as an international language was formed in the context of many cultural characteristics, historical factors and social changes. Today it plays an important role in international communications and is used to achieve various

goals. Learning English allows a deeper understanding of the culture of English-speaking countries, and intercultural communication requires taking into account cultural differences and language features. Historical, sociocultural and linguistic factors influence the use and dissemination of the English language in various cultural contexts. Understanding these factors helps to use English more effectively in intercultural communication, taking into account various cultural nuances.

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